

WT

N74D

% GFP positive cells

T5Cyp Nup153_1

T5Cyp Nup153_1

Time of Washout (hr)

WT

N74D

WT

T5Cyp dsRed_3

N74D

T5Cyp dsRed_3

T5Cyp Nup153_3

T5Cyp Nup153_3

Time of Washout (hr)

% GFP positive cells